

Jesus, son of Mary, said: "O Allah, our Lord, send down to us a table from the heaven to be for us a festival for the first of us and the last of us and a sign from You. And provide for us, and You are the best of providers." (Al-Ma'idah: 114)

First: Research on the Indication of the Word "Al-Sur" in the Holy Quran

A Foundational Study in Light of Arabic Lexicons and Exegetes' Statements, with a Parallel Analysis of the Verses of Blowing and Revival

Level One

Researcher: Alaa H. Al-Turfi Alaa Hussein Abbas

Abstract

This research is a foundational study aiming to determine the meaning of the word "Al-Sur" in the Holy Quran, a word that appears in the context of the blowing for the Day of Resurrection in the Almighty's saying: "And the Horn is blown, and whoever is in the heavens and whoever is on the earth falls dead, except whom Allah wills. Then it is blown again, and at once they are standing, looking on." (Az-Zumar: 68). Scholars' opinions have varied regarding its meaning: is it the horn that is blown into (the majority opinion) or is it the plural of "Surah" meaning forms and bodies (an opinion indicated by Az-Zajjaj and At-Tabarsi, and explicitly stated by Imam Al-Hasan bin Ali bin Abi Talib, though they did not explain its details). The research seeks to present a foundational reading that favors the second opinion through an integrated methodology combining linguistic foundation, exegetical analysis, and parallelism with Quranic stories of revival, relying on early Salaf statements.

The research also includes a foundational study of the word "buq" (trumpet) in light of Arabic lexicons, demonstrating that this word was not known at the time of Prophethood nor in the Holy Quran, and that it entered Arabic after the Islamic conquests. The research proceeds from an inductive study of the roots of the letters (S-W-R) in major lexicons, to extract a central linguistic equation: inclination → form → Sartahu, derived from Al-Azhari's rule: "Everything you incline from its direction, you have indeed made it a form (Sartahu)." It presents the exegetical disagreement, discusses the majority's evidence, analyzes the meanings of blowing and fainting (Sa'q), and presents the four models of revival (Adam, Abraham, Jesus, Mary) which confirm that revival occurs through forming a body (form) and then blowing the spirit.

The research dedicates a section to the Prophetic hadith "Al-Sur is a horn (Qarn) that is blown into", and demonstrates through an inductive study of the meaning of "Qarn" in the Quran (nation, generation) that this meaning is most consistent with the objectives of prophetic interpretation, while acknowledging that the word "Qarn" in the language also has another meaning: the instrument, and that the hadith can accommodate both meanings. The research also reviews the verses of "Labithna" (We have remained) in the Quran which prove that after resurrection people tried to determine the duration they felt, and their estimates differed, and that the Quran expressed the unity of these estimates with the indefinite word "Sa'ah" (hour) which indicates a period of cutting off and interruption.

The research concludes that "Al-Sur" as the plural of "Surah" meaning forms and bodies is closest to the Quranic context, that the first blow causes fainting (unconsciousness) and the second causes wakefulness and perception, and that the time between them is not felt. The research offers an addition to Quranic studies through its integrated methodology, central linguistic equation, exegetical model in light of revival stories, and reliance on the statement of the Prophet's grandson, Imam Al-Hasan bin Ali, regarding this meaning.

Introduction

Praise be to Allah who created and proportioned, who destined and guided, and peace be upon His chosen Prophet, upon the prophets and their families, companions, and those who follow his guidance.

One of the most important objectives of Quranic sciences is attention to its words and delving into their linguistic meanings with which revelation descended, for understanding the Quranic text is only achieved by invoking the meanings of words in the language of the Arabs who were addressed with it. Among the Quranic words that have intrigued both early and late researchers is the word "Al-Sur" appearing in the context of the blowing for the Day of Resurrection, in the Almighty's saying: "And the Horn is blown, and whoever is in the heavens and whoever is on the earth falls dead, except whom Allah wills. Then it is blown again, and at once they are standing, looking on" (Az-Zumar: 68), and in other verses. Scholars' statements have multiplied regarding the meaning of this word: Is it the horn that is blown into, as held by the majority of exegetes and linguists? Or is it the plural of "Surah" meaning the forms and bodies into which the resurrection blow is blown? This disagreement is not merely verbal; it is central to understanding the scene of the blowing and comprehending the implications of the Quranic texts.

Methodology of the Research: This research follows an integrated methodology combining:

The inductive method: to trace the words of the root (S-W-R) in lexicons, induct the ten verses of Al-Sur, the verses of "Labithna", and the verses of "Qarn" in the Holy Quran.

The analytical–semantic method: to analyze the meanings of words in their linguistic and Quranic contexts, and extract linguistic equations from the texts of the imams.

The comparative method: to compare the statements of exegetes (the majority and the other opinion), and between the different verses of blowing.

The analogical method: to connect the story of Abraham in reviving the birds with the verses of blowing, and the story of Jesus creating birds with the verses of blowing into Al–Sur.

The critical method: in studying the hadiths explaining Al–Sur, distinguishing authentic from weak, and critiquing the interpretation of "Qarn" as "buq" (trumpet) in light of lexicons and linguistic history.

This research aims to present a foundational study of the root (S–W–R) in major Arabic lexicons, investigating the relationship between its original meaning of inclination and its branch meaning of form, then discusses the disagreement over the interpretation of "Al–Sur" in light of that, along with an analysis of the meaning of blowing and fainting in language and the Quran, leading to a preference for one of the two views in a manner consistent with contextual implications and grammatical rules, relying on the linguistic equation extracted from the texts of the imams: inclination → form → Sartahu, and relying on the parallel between the verses of blowing and the story of Abraham in reviving the birds, the story of Moses in the faint of revelation, His saying "On the Day He will call you and you will respond", and the miracle of Jesus creating birds.

First Topic: Linguistic Foundation of the Root (S–W–R)

First Requirement: The Linguistic Root and Original Meaning (Inclination and Joining)

The first to establish the methodology of great derivation was Imam Al-Khalil bin Ahmad Al-Farahidi in the lexicon "Al-Ain", where he made the root (S–W–R) one of the origins indicating a single meaning from which all derived words branch. Al-Khalil said: "Al-Sawr: inclination. And I have formed (Sawwartu) the thing: I turned it and shaped it into its form." This text declares that inclination is the original dynamic meaning, and that forming (Taswir) is directing and inclining the thing from its initial state to an intended form.

Ibn Faris in "Maqayis Al-Lughah" confirms this meaning, saying: "The Sad, Waw, and Ra is a single root indicating inclination in a thing, then from it branches the meaning of form (Surah) and shaping (Taswir)."

The meaning expands in "Lisan Al-Arab" by Ibn Manzur to include joining and gathering. He says: "Sara the thing yasuruhu sawran: if he turned it and inclined it. Al-Surah: the shape and form. Al-Sur: the horn that is blown into, named Sur because it yasuru – i.e., it inclines the sound of the blower." Here Ibn Manzur combines inclination and joining, because the horn is a joined, hollow structure. In "Taj Al-Arus" by Al-Zubaidi: "Al-Sur: the horn, named for the joining and gathering of its parts."

Conclusion: The original meaning of the root (S–W–R) in the lexicons revolves around inclination as an act of direction and change, from which the meaning of joining emerges as a quality of the resulting form.

Second Requirement: The Relationship Between Inclination and Form (Al–Azhari's Rule and the Linguistic Equation)

In "Tahdhib Al–Lughah" by Al–Azhari, there is a precise text linking inclination and form in the form of a comprehensive linguistic rule: "Everything you incline from its direction, you have indeed made it a form (Sartahu)."

Explanation: "Miltahu" – you inclined and changed it. "An wajhihi" – from its original direction and place. "Sartahu" – from the verb "Sara yasuru" meaning you made it a form. This rule shows that the form (Surah) is not just a static shape, but rather the fixed trace that results after the act of inclination and direction. So, everything that is inclined from its original state acquires a new form.

Accordingly, the basic linguistic equation can be derived: Inclination → Form → Sartahu. That is, inclination is the act that generates a new form, and this act is precisely "Sartahu" derived from "Sara yasuru". This equation will serve as the axis we rely on to understand the meanings of words derived from the root.

Third Requirement: The Development of Meaning to Surah and Sur

Through inductive study of linguistic texts, the development of meaning can be traced: The trilateral verb "Sara yasuru" indicates inclination, turning, and changing, as in their saying: "Sara ash-shay'a 'an wajhihi" meaning he inclined it. Its verbal noun "Sawran" is used to indicate inclination itself. "Al-Surah" (with Damm on the Sad) is the name for the form that has settled after inclination; it is the result of the process. "Al-Sur" (with Damm on the Sad and Sukun on the Waw) is the name for the horn; either because it inclines the blower's sound, or because it is a structure of joined parts, or because it forms (yusawwir) sounds into an audible form.

This development shows that Surah and Sur are branches of a single root meaning inclination, but they diverged in terminological usage: Surah for visual form, and Sur for the blowing instrument.

Fourth Requirement: The Proximity Between the Roots (S-W-R) and (S-Y-R) – The Meaning of Becoming (Sayrurah)

The origin of the root (S-Y-R) in the lexicons returns to the meaning of ending and transformation. Ibn Faris in "Maqayis Al-Lughah" says: "The Sad, Ya, and Ra is a single root indicating ending at a thing and returning to it." This meaning is close to the meaning of (S-W-R) which revolves around inclination and direction. Both share the meaning of transformation and change. The common ground between the two roots is the concept of "Sayrurah" (becoming), which is the name for the process of transitioning from one state to another.

This common ground explains the multiplicity of recitations in the story of Abraham (Al-Baqarah: 260): "Then take four birds and Fasurhunna (make them incline/come) to you." The recitation with Damm (Surahunna) is from (S-W-R) meaning make them into forms, and the recitation with

Kasr (Sirhunna) is from (S–Y–R) meaning cut them or direct them. The multiplicity of recitations indicates that the verb carries both meanings together: transformation into a new form (Sayrurah) and giving form (Taswir).

The comprehensive equation: S–W–R (inclination) → S–Y–R (becoming/transformation) → S–W–R (form/shape).

This confirms that "Al–Sur" (the forms) are the result of a divine becoming process that began with inclination (the command "Be") and ended with the new form into which the spirit is blown.

Fifth Requirement: The Plural of "Surah" on the pattern "Fu'l" – Reason for the Sukun on the Waw

It might be problematic for the view that "Al–Sur" is the plural of "Surah" that the word in the Quranic script is written "Al–Sur" with Damm on the Sad and Sukun on the Waw. If it were the plural of "Surah", the qiyas (analogical measure) would require it to be written "Al–Suwar" with Fatha on the Waw. However, this problem is resolved if we know that the plural of "Fu'lah" on "Fu'l" (with Sukun on the 'ayn) is a known pattern in Arabic for lightening.

Ibn Jinni in "Al–Khasa'is" said: "The Arabs choose the easier pronunciation. If the weight is heavy, they shift to what is lighter." The original plural of "Surah" would have been "Suwar" (weight Fu'al) with a Fatha on the Waw, which is heavy due to the combination of Dammah and Fathah, so the Waw was made silent (sukun) for lightening, becoming "Sur" (weight Fu'l).

This lightening has parallels in the Quran, including: Busr (plural of Busurah), Suqf (plural of Suquf), Rutab (plural of Rutabah), Ghuraf (plural of Ghurfah), which appears in the Quran: "For them are chambers (Ghuraf) above which are chambers" (Az-Zumar: 20). The significance of this lightening is not merely morphological but also has a semantic dimension: lightening indicates speed and readiness, which is consistent with "Al-Sur" (the forms) being prepared quickly to receive the blowing of the spirit.

Second Topic: The Meaning of "Al-Sur" in the Quran Between Horn and Forms

First Requirement: The Majority Opinion: Al-Sur = The Horn

The majority of exegetes and linguists hold that the intended meaning of "Al-Sur" in the verses of blowing is the horn that is blown into. They rely on several pieces of evidence: The mutawatir recitation: The word is written in the Quranic script without an alif, and its recitation as "Al-Sur" (with Damm on the Sad and Sukun on the Waw) is mutawatir from the Prophet. Prophetic hadiths: It is reported in authentic Sunnah that Al-Sur is a horn. Linguistic consensus: Al-Qurtubi said in his Tafsir: "The people of language unanimously agree that Al-Sur is the horn." Quranic context: The blowing into Al-Sur is repeated in more than one place, and the verses speak of two blows, which is consistent with Al-Sur being a single instrument blown into twice.

Second Requirement: The Other Opinion: Al-Sur is the Plural of Surah (Forms and Bodies)

In contrast to the majority opinion, some scholars have suggested the possibility that "Al-Sur" is the plural of "Surah" meaning bodies and forms. This view is attributed to: Az-Zajjaj (d. 311 AH)

in "Ma'ani Al-Quran wa l'rabihi": "It is said: it is the plural of Surah, as in Suqf (plural of Saqf)." At-Tabarsi (d. 548 AH) in "Majma' Al-Bayan": "It is said: it is the plural of Surah, as they say Busr in plural of Busurah." Qatadah and Abu Ubaidah, as mentioned by Ibn Al-Jawzi in "Zad Al-Masir": "Qatadah and Abu Ubaidah said: it is the plural of Surah."

Added to these statements is an older and more reliable one, narrated by Sheikh Al-Tusi in his Tafsir "Al-Tibyan" from Imam Al-Hasan bin Ali bin Abi Talib, the grandson of the Messenger of Allah, where he said: "Al-Hasan said: Al-Sur is the plural of Surah, meaning when the spirits are blown into them and they are brought back to life." This statement – from Imam Al-Hasan bin Ali (d. 50 AH) – represents strong evidence from the first century AH, from a unique scholarly figure. Imam Al-Hasan is the grandson of the Messenger of Allah, the son of his daughter Fatima Al-Zahra, raised directly by the Prophet, grew up in the house of prophethood, and learned from his father Ali bin Abi Talib and the companions. Ibn Hajar Al-Asqalani said in "Al-Isabah": "Al-Hasan bin Ali bin Abi Talib, the grandson of the Messenger of Allah and his sweet basil, born in Sha'ban of year three of Hijra, and the Prophet raised him." Imam Al-Hasan's interpretation of Al-Sur as the plural of "Surah" proves that this meaning was known in early exegesis from the first century AH, and that the matter was subject to consideration and ijtiḥad among the Salaf.

Their evidence – in addition to the above – includes: The morphological pattern: The plural of "Surah" on the pattern "Fu'l" has parallels in Arabic. Semantic appropriateness: Blowing into the forms and bodies is more fitting for the meaning of resurrection. Context: Some verses may indicate blowing directly into the bodies, such as His saying: "Then when the Horn is blown with one blast" (Al-Haqqah: 13).

Third Requirement: The Meaning of the Definite Article "Al-" in "Al-Sur"

The word "Al-Sur" appears in all ten verses of blowing with the definite article "Al-", never appearing as indefinite even once. This uniformity in definition has important implications.

First: "Al-" for generalization or mental reference: The definite article for the genus indicates that the intended meaning is the genus of forms (Al-Sur) which is meant to encompass all.

Second: Uniformity in definition: All ten verses of Al-Sur come with "Al-Sur" defined with "Al-", which is consistent with it being the forms that are recreated.

Third: The difference between "Nufikha fi al-Sur" (blown into Al-Sur) and "Nufikha bi al-Sur" (blown with Al-Sur): If "Al-Sur" were the instrument, it would be more appropriate to say "Nufikha bi al-Sur" (with the instrument particle "bi"). But the verses say "Nufikha fi al-Sur" ("fi" for container or spatiality), so Al-Sur here is the container into which blowing occurs, i.e., the forms.

Fourth Requirement: Application of the Hypothesis to the Ten Verses of Al-Sur

Below is a presentation of how the interpretation of "Al-Sur" as the plural of "Surah" (the forms) applies to the ten verses of blowing.

First: Surat Az-Zumar (68): The first blow – blowing into the forms, so physiological life enters and they faint (unconsciousness). The second blow – blowing into the same forms, so they awake and stand looking.

Second: Surat An-Naml (87): A single blow causes terror, which is the second blow that brings them out of their unconsciousness to wakefulness.

Third: Surat Ya-Sin (51): A single blow brings them out of their graves, which is the second blow.

Fourth: Surat Al-Haqqah (13-15): A single blow is the second blow at which the greater resurrection occurs.

Fifth: Surat Al-Kahf (99): The second blow gathers people after they were dead and then physiologically revived.

Sixth: Surat Ta-Ha (102): A single blow is the second, followed by the gathering.

Seventh: Surat Al-Mu'minun (101): A single blow (the second) at which worldly relationships end.

Eighth: Surat Al-Muddaththir (8): "An-Naqr" can be interpreted as the second blow.

Ninth: Surat Al-An'am (73): Blowing into Al-Sur indicates the beginning of the Day of Resurrection.

Conclusion: All verses can be interpreted with "Al-Sur" as forms without strain or difficulty, with the two blows distributed between fainting (unconsciousness) and awakening (standing).

Third Topic: The Meaning of Blowing (Nafkh) and Fainting (Sa'q) in Language and the Quran

First Requirement: Linguistic Foundation of Blowing (Nafkh)

The origin of the root (N-F-KH) in lexicons returns to the meaning of swelling and rising, as in "Maqayis Al-Lughah": "Nafkh: a sound root indicating swelling and rising." In "Kitab Al-Ain": "Nafkh: expelling air from the mouth."

Second Requirement: The Linguistic Meaning of Fainting (Sa'q)

In Arabic lexicons, Sa'q is not restricted to death; its origin is fainting and unconsciousness due to the severity of an event. Lisan Al-Arab: "Al-Sa'q: fainting. It is said: Sa'iqā ar-rajulu yas'aqu sa'qan and su'aqan: if he lost consciousness." Taj Al-Arus: "Al-Sa'q: fainting. Some specialized it as the death of the heart, meaning the departure of the soul. It can also be used for death." Al-Mufradat: "Al-Sa'q: a type of fainting that prevents discernment, and it may be death."

Third Requirement: Evidence of Sa'q in the Quran (Story of Moses and His People)

Sa'q appears in the Quran in two main places indicating it is unconsciousness, not death.

First: The sa'q of Moses upon his Lord's manifestation to the mountain: "And when his Lord appeared to the mountain, He made it crumble, and Moses fell down unconscious (Sa'iqah). Then when he recovered, he said: Exalted are You, I repent to You." (Al-A'raf: 143)

Second: The sa'q of the Children of Israel: "So the thunderbolt (Al-Sa'iqah) seized them for their wrongdoing" (An-Nisa: 153). So Moses fainted and then recovered, and the thunderbolt seized the Children of Israel and then they were revived. This confirms that Sa'q can be severe unconsciousness, and can be death followed by revival, but its origin is fainting.

Fourth Requirement: The Difference Between the Fainting of the Inhabitants of the Heavens and the Inhabitants of the Earth

In the verse of Az-Zumar: "So fell dead (fainted) whoever was in the heavens and whoever was on the earth." It is noted that the fainting of the inhabitants of the heavens (angels) differs in its cause from the fainting of the inhabitants of the earth.

Fainting of the inhabitants of the heavens: Mentioned in Surat An-Naml: "And on the Day the Horn is blown, and terrified will be whoever is in the heavens and whoever is on the earth" (An-Naml: 87). The angels are seized by terror from the horror of the scene.

Fainting of the inhabitants of the earth: It is a physiological fainting resulting from the sudden return of life to bodies after their long death.

This understanding is confirmed by the context of Surat Az-Zumar. The verse preceding the blowing verse (Az-Zumar: 67) establishes that humans were dead before the blow, then the first blow comes to return life to them, and they faint, then the second blow to awaken them. This sequence – death → revival (fainting) → awakening (standing) – proves that fainting is a physiological revival, not a death.

Fifth Requirement: The Martyrs, the Exception, and the Meaning of the Greatest Terror

The Quran describes martyrs as alive with their Lord, provided for (Aal-Imran: 169, Al-Baqarah: 154). This explains why they are among the exceptions in the two verses of blowing (An-Naml: 87, Az-Zumar: 68). Also, His saying: "The greatest terror will not grieve them" (Al-Anbiya: 103) confirms that they are among those excepted from terror. And His saying in Surat Ar-Rahman: "Everyone upon the earth will perish" (Ar-Rahman: 26–27) specifies perishing only for those upon the earth.

Sixth Requirement: The Meaning of "Everyone upon it will perish" – The Quranic Foundation of Perishing

The Almighty said in Surat Ar-Rahman: "Everyone upon the earth will perish. And there remains the Face of your Lord, Owner of Majesty and Honor" (Ar-Rahman: 26–27). The word "Fānin" is derived from the root (F–N–Y), whose origin in Arabic is cessation and disappearance. Reflecting on the context of the verse, one notices that the perishing mentioned is the perishing of those upon the earth, encompassing humans, animals, plants, and inanimate objects. This specification has significance in understanding the verses of blowing, distinguishing between the fainting of the earth's inhabitants (after life is restored) and the fainting of the heavens' inhabitants (terror,

not death). And if perishing is total cessation, that necessarily entails the cessation of the sense of time. This meaning is confirmed by the verses of "Labithna" (We have remained). The verse of Ar-Rahman establishes that death in this world is perishing, meaning that after death, a person does not sense time at all, and any sense of time after resurrection must have begun after life was restored.

Fourth Topic: The Story of Abraham – The Original Exegetical Model for the Verses of Blowing

First Requirement: Abraham's Question and the Practical Answer

The Almighty said: "And when Abraham said: My Lord, show me how You give life to the dead. He said: Have you not believed? He said: Yes, but that my heart be at rest. He said: Then take four birds and Fasurhunna (make them incline/come) to you, then place on every mountain a part of them, then call them; they will come to you in haste. And know that Allah is Exalted in Might, Wise." (Al-Baqarah: 260). This verse is not merely a historical story; it is a practical experiment that Abraham wanted to reassure his heart, so Allah showed him how the dead are revived.

Second Requirement: The Stages of Revival in the Story of Abraham

Stage One: "Fasurhunna ilayka" – The formation of complete bodies and their gathering. After this stage, the birds were fully formed and not scattered, but they did not come in haste. The word "Fasurhunna" – with Damm on the Sad – is from (S-W-R) meaning make them into forms,

or from (S-Y-R) meaning cut them or direct them. Both recitations are mutawatir, and each indicates transformation into a new form (Sayrurah) and giving form (Taswir).

Stage Two: "Then place on every mountain a part of them" – Distributing the birds over the mountains. It should be noted that the word "juz'an" (part) in the verse does not mean the physical dismemberment of a single bird into parts, but rather a group or division of each type of the four birds. Az-Zajjaj said in "Ma'ani Al-Quran": "The meaning of 'juz'an' is a group from each one of them." Al-Tabari said in "Jami' Al-Bayan": "The correct view is that Allah commanded him to place on every mountain from each of the four that He commanded him to slaughter a part, i.e., a piece and a group." Ibn Ashur said in "Al-Tahrir wa Al-Tanwir": "Al-Juz' (part) means the group and division of something. It does not mean the fragmentation of a single bird into limbs, but rather the distribution of each type on a mountain such that on each mountain there is a part of each type."

This understanding has an important implication for the exegetical model: The distribution was not a fragmentation of a single form into scattered parts needing collection, but rather a distribution of complete groups over the mountains, confirming that the forms remained complete after the stage of "Sarr", and that the distribution was to show Allah's power to gather them from different places after they had been gathered with him. This aligns with the research's conclusion that after the first blow, the forms (Al-Sur) are complete and physiologically alive, then the second blow gives them consciousness and perception, so they rise from scattered places.

Stage Three: "Then call them; they will come to you in haste" – The divine call that grants consciousness, perception, and voluntary movement, so the birds gather from their scattered places to Abraham in haste.

The Extracted Pattern: Formation of a form (Sarr) → Distribution and scattering (groups) → Call (awakening and coming)

Third Requirement: Applying the Abrahamic Model to the Verses of Blowing

The first blow in Az-Zumar = the stage of "Fasurhunna": "Sarr" was transforming the bird from the state of death into complete forms capable of life. This parallels the first blow that causes physiological life (fainting). Just as after "Sarr" the bird was existent but did not come in haste, so too after the first blow the forms are alive but in a state of unconsciousness.

The second blow in Az-Zumar = the stage of "Then call them": The call is what made the birds come in haste. This parallels the second blow that causes standing and looking. It also parallels His saying in Surat Al-Isra: "On the Day He will call you and you will respond" (Al-Isra: 52).

Fourth Requirement: The Meaning of "Thumma" (Then) in Light of the Abrahamic Model

In the story of Abraham, "Thumma" is used twice: "Thumma place" and "Thumma call". "Thumma" here indicates sequence with delay (a respite between stages). This is exactly what appears in the verse of Az-Zumar: "Thumma it is blown again" (Thumma nufikha fihi ukhra). It does not mean two separate blows, but rather two successive stages of one blow.

Fifth Requirement: Evidence from Surat Al-Qiyamah – The Two Stages of Re-creation

The Almighty said in Surat Al-Qiyamah: "Does man think that We will not assemble his bones? Yes, We are able to proportion his fingertips" (Al-Qiyamah: 3-4). These two verses represent evidence that the re-creation occurs in two stages. The first stage (assembling bones) parallels "formation of the form", and the second stage (proportioning fingertips) parallels the completion of the form and its readiness to receive the blowing of the spirit. Then He concludes: "Is not that able to give life to the dead?" (Al-Qiyamah: 40). This connection confirms that re-creation follows the pattern of the first creation.

Sixth Requirement: Conclusion

The story of Abraham is the exegetical key to understanding all the verses of blowing and revival in the Quran. It establishes a consistent pattern: Formation of a form (blow of physiological life) → a state of unconsciousness or waiting, then distribution and scattering (demonstration of Allah's power to gather from different places), then a divine call (blow of wakefulness and perception) → rising and coming in haste.

This model explains: Why Az-Zumar mentions two blows (detailing the two stages), why Ya-Sin and others mention one blow (focusing on the second stage), and why people say "Who has raised us?" (because they did not feel anything except the second stage).

Fifth Topic: The Evidence of the Creation of the Bird for Jesus and Mary – The Meaning of the Two Pronouns

First Requirement: Verses of Creating the Bird for Jesus

Aal-Imran (49): "I create for you from clay like the form of a bird, then I blow into it (fihi), and it becomes a bird." The pronoun is masculine (fihi) referring back to "the bird" after its completion.

Al-Ma'idah (110): "And when you create from clay like the form of a bird by My permission, then you blow into it (fiha), and it becomes a bird." The pronoun is feminine (fiha) referring back to "like the form of the bird" before the spirit is blown.

Second Requirement: Verses of Mary

Al-Anbiya (91): "And she who guarded her chastity, so We blew into her (fiha) of Our spirit." The pronoun is feminine (fiha) referring back to the form into which the spirit was blown.

At-Tahrim (12): "And Mary, daughter of Imran, who guarded her chastity, so We blew into him (fihi) of Our spirit." The pronoun is masculine (fihi) referring back to Jesus after his completion.

Third Requirement: The Significance of the Difference in Pronouns

The blowing is one, but the Quran used two pronouns to distinguish two stages: the first stage (the feminine form) and the second stage (the created masculine being). This difference clarifies the two stages of revival: the stage of the form (feminine) and the stage of the created being (masculine).

Sixth Topic: Application of the Linguistic Equation and Parallelism to the Verse of Blowing

First Requirement: Interpreting "Al-Sur" in Light of the Linguistic Equation and Parallelism

Interpreting "Al-Sur" as forms makes the verse of Az-Zumar consistently meaningful with the root's origin. The linguistic equation: Inclination → Form → Sartahu.

Its application: The first inclination: creating the form (body) and shaping it from dust. The first form: the physiologically alive body after the first blow (which is "Al-Sur"). The second inclination (Sartahu): transforming the form from the state of unconsciousness to the state of wakefulness. The second form: the conscious, active body that stands and looks.

Second Requirement: Directing the Pronoun and the Exception in Light of Understanding Fainting as Unconsciousness

The majority said: The pronoun in "Then it is blown again (Thumma nufikha fihi ukhra)" refers to Al-Sur, and if it were the plural of Surah, the bodies would have perished. The answer: The fainting was not death but unconsciousness, and the forms remain.

Third Requirement: Directing the Masculine Pronoun in "Thumma nufikha fihi ukhra" – A Morphological Study

Some who hold that "Al-Sur" is the plural of "Surah" raise a morphological problem: How can the masculine pronoun "fihi" refer to a feminine plural? The answer is from two perspectives.

First perspective: The broken plural of the feminine (Fu'lah – Fu'l) is often treated as masculine in Arabic, and the masculine pronoun refers back to it. Among the Quranic evidence: "And for them are chambers (Ghuraf) above which are chambers (Ghuraf)" (Az-Zumar: 20). "Ghuraf" is the plural of "Ghurfa", which is feminine.

Second perspective: The pronoun in "fihi" does not refer directly to the word "Al-Sur", but rather to the implied meaning derived from it, which is "the body" or "the created being", which is masculine. This is a case of referring the pronoun to the meaning rather than the wording, a known Arabic style.

Fourth Requirement: Linking the Second Blow to the Divine Call

The Almighty said: "On the Day He will call you and you will respond with His praise" (Al-Isra: 52). The call in Al-Isra = the second blow, and the response = "and at once they are standing, looking on."

Seventh Topic: The Hadith on Al-Sur and Qarn in the Quran – A Foundational Approach

Introduction

One of the most prominent challenges facing the hypothesis is the authentic hadith: "Al-Sur is a horn (Qarn) that is blown into." This topic presents a foundational reading of the hadith, demonstrating that the Prophet – when he interpreted "Al-Sur" as "Qarn" – used an authentic Arabic word that appears in the Quran, and that the word "Qarn" in the Quran only appears in the meaning of nation and generation. It also shows that the word "buq" (trumpet) was not known at the time of Prophethood but entered Arabic after the Islamic conquests.

First Requirement: The Text of the Hadith and a Statement That It Does Not Contain the Word "Buq"

The hadith was narrated by Imam Ahmad in Al-Musnad, Abu Dawud, Al-Tirmidhi, and Al-Hakim, from Abdullah bin Amr bin Al-As, may Allah be pleased with them both, who said: "A Bedouin came to the Prophet and said: What is Al-Sur? He said: A horn (Qarn) that is blown into." It is an authentic hadith. The foundational observation: In this hadith, the Prophet did not say "buq". The word "buq" does not appear in the prophetic text, nor in the Holy Quran. The Prophet used an authentic Arabic word that appears in the Quran, which is "Qarn".

Second Requirement: "Al-Qarn" in the Holy Quran – The Meaning of Nation

Inductive study of the Quranic verses shows that the word "Qarn" (singular) and "Qurun" (plural) appears in more than twenty places meaning nation or past generation, not meaning an instrument. The Almighty said: "Have they not seen how many a generation (Qarn) before them We have destroyed?" (Al-An'am: 6). "Then We produced after them another generation (Qarnan akhareen)" (Al-Mu'minun: 31). "And how many a generation (Qarn) before them have We destroyed?" (Maryam: 74).

Ibn Manzur said: "Al-Qarn: the past nation of people." Al-Raghib said: "Al-Qarn: the generation of people who coexist in one time."

Third Requirement: "Buq" – A Foundational Linguistic Study (A Foreign Loanword)

This requirement addresses the linguistic root of the word "buq" and its entry into Arabic.

First: Statements of language imams: Ibn Duraid said: "As for Al-Buq: it is something that is blown into, but I do not know its authenticity." Al-Azhari narrated from Shammar bin Hamdawayh: "I have not heard of Al-Buq in falsehood except here." Ibn Faris said: "The Ba, Waw, and Qaf is not a reliable root, and I have no sound word for it."

Second: The origin of the word: Researchers agree that "Buq" has a Latin/Greek origin from *buccina*.

Third: Non-occurrence of "Buq" in foundational texts: It does not appear in the Quran, nor in the Mu'allaqat, nor in pre-Islamic poetry.

Fourth Requirement: Understanding the Hadith "Al-Sur is a horn blown into" – Between Linguistic Fact and Quranic Interpretation

This research does not deny that the word "Qarn" in the Arabic language can be used for the blowing instrument (which is a valid linguistic meaning). However, the important point is that this meaning does not appear anywhere in the Quran, and the Prophet – in the context of interpreting the Quran – relied on the language in which the Quran was revealed.

A reconciliation between the two meanings can be made by saying: The Prophet used the word "Qarn" because it combines both meanings – the meaning of the instrument (which is the apparent meaning of the word) and the meaning of the nation (which is the inner Quranic meaning) – so that the single word points to the great cosmic reality: that Al-Sur (the forms) is the Qarn (the human nation) that is blown into with the resurrection blow, and that through an instrument which is also called Qarn. With this combination, the hadith remains sound in its apparent meaning, profound in its inner meaning, and does not conflict with interpreting Al-Sur as forms. It has been established that this meaning of Al-Sur – as the plural of Surah – was known in early exegesis, as narrated from Imam Al-Hasan bin Ali, the grandson of the Messenger of Allah.

Fifth Requirement: Israfil – A Critical Study of the Infiltration of Concepts

The name "Israfil" does not appear anywhere in the Holy Quran. The Quran describes the scene of the blowing into Al-Sur without naming the doer. The Almighty says: "And the Horn is blown, and whoever is in the heavens and whoever is on the earth falls dead" (Az-Zumar: 68). This silence is significant: if specifying the name of the angel were among matters of religion, the Quran would have clarified it.

The name has origins in Judeo-Christian tradition, where it is believed to correspond to the angel Raphael, Uriel, or Seraphiel. The name entered Islamic tradition through Isra'iliyyat (Jewish

narratives) and later books of exegesis and stories. Verified Islamic scholars – such as Ibn Kathir and Ibn Taymiyyah – have pointed out that these details are not from the authentic Islamic text. This supports that interpreting "Al-Sur" as forms is closest to the Quranic text, and that later details (Israfil, the trumpet) are later scholarly ijihad.

Eighth Topic: The Evidence of "Sa'ah" (Hour) – The Indication of the Verses of "Labithna" (We remained) on the Duration Between the Two Blows

Introduction

After the research favored that "Al-Sur" is the plural of "Surah", and that the first blow causes unconsciousness and the second causes wakefulness, a question arises: How long was the duration that people felt between the two blows? This topic addresses this question through an inductive study of the verses of "Labithna" in the Quran.

First Requirement: The Indefinite "Sa'ah" – The Linguistic Origin

In Kitab Al-Ain: "Al-Sa'ah: a piece of time. And the indefinite: a piece of time whose limit is not defined." In Maqayis Al-Lughah: "The Sin, Waw, and 'Ayn is a single root indicating cutting off and interruption." In Al-Mufradat: "Al-Sa'ah: the smallest of the times by which time is measured. And His saying: 'They remained no more than an hour' is an indication that death was a fainting spell."

Second Requirement: Inductive Study of the Verses of "Labithna" – The Different Estimates

The verses of "Labithna" appear in several places, all describing people's feeling after resurrection that they remained only a very short period, but the estimates differed.

First: Ta-Ha (103-104): The criminals said "ten days" or "a day."

Second: Al-Mu'minun (112-113): The general people said "a day or part of a day."

Third: Yunus (45): The general people said "an hour of the day."

Fourth: Ar-Rum (55): The criminals said "less than an hour."

Fifth: Al-Ahqaf (35): The general people said "an hour of the day."

Sixth: An-Nazi'at (46): The general people said "an evening or its morning."

Commonality: All indicate extreme shortness of duration.

Third Requirement: Analysis of the Difference – Attempts at Determination

The estimates differed due to differences among people (the criminals in Ta-Ha were "blue-eyed" and estimated a bit longer) and differences in situations (some verses describe the moment of gathering, others the moment of judgment). This difference confirms that they did not feel real time, but rather tried to estimate a very short duration.

Fourth Requirement: The Duration They Felt Is the Duration Between the Two Blows

Death is a perishing with no sensation: "Every soul will taste death" (Aal-Imran: 185) – "tasting" here is cessation, not sensation.

Temporal sequence: Death (perishing) → no sensation. Formation of forms → no sensation. First blow (life enters) → beginning of sensation. Unconsciousness (fainting) → confused sensation. Second blow (awakening) → full sensation.

After awakening, people thought that all of death was only the short duration they felt between the two blows.

The meaning of "Marqad" (place of sleep) in Ya-Sin (52): The grave is called a "sleeping place" because the dead person is like a sleeper (unconscious).

Fifth Requirement: The Verse "From it We created you" – Confirmation of Re-creation from the Earth

The Almighty said: "From it (the earth) We created you, and into it We will return you, and from it We will bring you out another time" (Ta-Ha: 55). This verse confirms that re-creation is from the earth, meaning that the bodies that perished are re-created from the earth itself. The verse mentions three stages: The first creation: "From it We created you." The re-creation (new construction): "And into it We will return you" (this is the stage of forming the new forms – Al-Sur). The bringing out: "And from it We will bring you out another time" (this is the stage of emerging from the graves after the completion of resurrection).

The word "tartatan ukhra" (another time) carries the meaning of bringing out once again after re-creation, and "al-ukhra" indicates that this re-creation is the second genesis.

Ninth Topic: The Meaning of "Kun Fayakun" (Be, and it is) – A Linguistic and Semantic Foundation and a Parallel to the Two Blows

Introduction

The formula "Kun Fayakun" appears in the Holy Quran in seven places, most notably related to the creation of the heavens and the earth and the revival of the dead. It appears in various contexts confirming that when Allah's will is attached to a thing, it happens instantly. It is notable that this formula appears in two complementary contexts: the context of general creation (Al-An'am: 73, Al-Baqarah: 117, Ya-Sin: 82, Ghafir: 68), and the context of the miracle of Jesus in creating birds and reviving the dead (Aal-Imran: 49, Al-Ma'idah: 110). Additionally, the verse of Al-An'am connects "Kun Fayakun" with the blowing into Al-Sur in a single context, which makes this requirement a natural extension of the research and contributes to strengthening the hypothesis that "Al-Sur" is the plural of "Surah" meaning forms and bodies.

First Requirement: The Foundation of the Fa (then/so) in "Fayakun" – The Linguistic Ruling and Meaning

First: The Fa for causality and immediate sequence: The most common view is that the Fa in "Fayakun" is the Fa of causality, indicating that the occurrence (being) happens immediately after the command without delay. Sibawayh said in "Al-Kitab": "The Fa in their saying 'Kun Fayakun' is for immediate sequence, i.e., it occurs after the command without separation." Al-Zamakhshari said in "Al-Kashshaf": "The Fa is for immediate sequence, indicating that its existence occurs after the command without delay."

Second: The Fa is attached to a present tense verb with an implied "An": This is the view of the Kufan school. Al-Kisa'i and Al-Farra' said: The implied meaning is "Kun fa an yakuna" or "fa an yakuna", then "an" was dropped and the verb is raised on isti'naf (resumption) or subjunctive on the assumption of "an". Al-Farra' said in "Ma'ani Al-Quran": "The Fa in His saying 'Fayakun' is the response to the command, the implied meaning being: Kun fa in takun fayakun."

Third: The Fa for conjunction to the nominal or verbal sentence: Ibn Hisham said in "Mughni Al-Labib": "The Fa in 'Fayakun' is a conjunctive, linking the response clause to the command clause, and it indicates sequence and immediate succession."

Fourth: The temporal meaning of the Fa: The Fa indicates that the existence of the thing occurs immediately after the command, with no delay whatsoever. This means that the time interval between the command and existence is the shortest possible, almost nonexistent. Ibn Al-Qayyim said in "Madarij Al-Salikin": "The Fa in 'Fayakun' is the Fa of immediate sequence, indicating that

the existence of the created being is concurrent with the command, not delayed by the blink of an eye."

The difference between "Fa", "Thumma", and "Waw": If it were said "Kun thumma yakun", the meaning would be: sequence with delay (a respite). If it were said "Kun wa yakun", the meaning would be: combination without sequence. But "Kun Fayakun" means: sequence with immediate succession. Ibn Ashur said in "Al-Tahrir wa Al-Tanwir": "The choice of Fa over other conjunctive particles is to indicate that the 'being' is attached to the command without delay, unlike the Waw which does not indicate sequence, and unlike Thumma which indicates delay."

Second Requirement: "Kun" – The Creative Command, Not the Obligatory One

It might be problematic that the command "Kun" (Be) is directed only to an existing being capable of obedience. How can Allah command a non-existent thing to be, when non-existence cannot hear or understand?

The verified scholars answered that this command is not an obligatory command (like Allah's command to His servants to pray), but rather a creative command meaning creation. Ibn Malik said in "Sharh Al-Kafiyah Al-Shafiya": "Allah's command to a thing to be is a creative command, and the Fa in its response is for immediate sequence." Thus, the non-existent is not addressed; rather, the meaning is that when Allah's will is attached to the existence of something, it exists.

Al-Raghib Al-Isfahani said in "Al-Mufradat": "The meaning is not that when He says to a thing 'Be', it becomes the doer of its own being, but rather that it exists after the command." This

distinguishes between divine creation and human action: when a human says to another "Be", it requires the obedience of the commanded one, whereas Allah's saying "Be" is the very act of creation.

Third Requirement: "Kun Fayakun" in the Quran – Inductive Study of Contexts

The formula appears in seven Quranic places, including:

First: Al-Baqarah (117): "Originator of the heavens and the earth. When He decrees a matter, He only says to it: Be, and it is."

Second: Al-An'am (73): "And He is the one who created the heavens and the earth in truth. And the day He says: Be, and it is. His word is the truth. And His is the dominion on the day the Horn is blown."

Third: Aal-Imran (59): "Indeed, the example of Jesus in the sight of Allah is like that of Adam. He created him from dust, then said to him: Be, and he was."

Fourth: Ya-Sin (82): "His command is only when He intends a thing that He says to it: Be, and it is."

Fifth: Ghafir (68): "He is the one who gives life and causes death. And when He decrees a matter, He only says to it: Be, and it is."

Observations derived from the inductive study: The formula appears in the context of direct creation (heavens and earth, Adam). It appears in the context of revival (Ghafir: "He gives life and causes death"). It appears in the context of the day on which Al-Sur is blown (Al-An'am: 73).

Fourth Requirement: The Connection Between "Kun Fayakun" and Blowing into Al-Sur in the Verse of Al-An'am

The Almighty said: "And He is the one who created the heavens and the earth in truth. And the day He says: Be, and it is. His word is the truth. And His is the dominion on the day the Horn is blown" (Al-An'am: 73).

This verse connects two great matters: "The day He says: Be, and it is" – i.e., the Day of Resurrection when Allah says to creation "Be" and it is. "And His is the dominion on the day the Horn is blown" – i.e., the blow that precedes the resurrection.

The connection between "Kun Fayakun" and "the blowing into Al-Sur" in a single verse indicates that the blowing into Al-Sur is the practical application of "Kun Fayakun" on the Day of Resurrection. Just as "Kun" is the divine command, so the blow is the means by which this command is realized in the forms.

Fifth Requirement: The Story of Jesus – The Applied Model of "Kun Fayakun"

The Almighty said on the tongue of Jesus: "That I create for you from clay like the form of a bird, then I blow into it, and it becomes a bird by Allah's permission" (Aal-Imran: 49). This verse presents a practical, applied model of the principle of "Kun Fayakun":

The stage of formation: "I create for you from clay like the form of the bird" – this stage parallels the stage of forming the form (the clay).

The stage of blowing: "Then I blow into it" – this stage parallels the blowing of the spirit into the form.

The result: "And it becomes a bird" – the complete existence after the blowing.

The meaning of the Fa in "Fa'ankhukhu" and "Fayakunu": The Fa in "Fa'ankhukhu" is the Fa of immediate sequence, indicating that the blowing occurs immediately after the creation. The Fa in "Fayakunu" is the Fa of causality, indicating that the bird exists immediately after the blowing.

This correspondence between the structure of the verse and the structure of "Kun Fayakun" proves that Jesus – by Allah's permission – applied this principle in his miracle to be a sign to people of how the dead will be revived on the Day of Resurrection.

Sixth Requirement: Applying the "Kun Fayakun" Model to the Two Blows

Based on the above, the relationship between "Kun Fayakun" and the two blows can be formulated as follows:

In the context of general creation (Kun Fayakun): "Kun" is the divine command, the Fa is for immediate direct sequence, and "Fayakun" is the existence.

In the context of revival in the story of Jesus: "I create" is the formation of the form, "then I blow" is the blowing immediately, and "it becomes a bird" is the existence.

In the context of blowing into Al-Sur: The first blow is the formation of the forms (Al-Sur), then the respite between the two blows ("Thumma"), then the second blow with "and at once they are standing, looking on."

The important observation: The story of Jesus did not include a delay between formation and blowing (using the Fa for immediate sequence), while the verse of Az-Zumar mentions "Thumma" for delay between the two blows. This difference is significant: the first and second blows are two successive stages in a single process of revival, and the duration between them – although a respite – was not felt by people, as established in the eighth topic (the verses of "Labithna").

Seventh Requirement: The Indication of "Kun Fayakun" That Revival Does Not Require Intermediaries

The structure "Kun Fayakun" indicates that divine creation does not require causes or intermediaries, but is direct. This is consistent with the research's conclusion that "Al-Sur" is the

plural of "Surah" (the forms), and that the blowing into Al-Sur is a direct blowing into the bodies, without need for an external instrument (horn/trumpet). Ibn Al-Qayyim said in "Al-Sawa'iq Al-Mursala": "His saying 'Kun Fayakun' is evidence that when His will is attached to a thing, it happens instantly, without need for an instrument or time. Rather, will and existence are simultaneous, with no interval between them."

Eighth Requirement: Combining "Thumma" and "Fa" – Understanding the Stages of Revival

If we combine the meaning of "Thumma" in the verse of Az-Zumar and the meaning of "Fa" in the story of Jesus, we can understand the stages of revival as follows:

The stage of formation (the first blow): Allah creates the forms (Al-Sur) from the earth and places physiological life within them. This stage parallels "I create" in the story of Jesus, and parallels "Kun" in the creative command.

The delay (Thumma): Between formation and wakefulness there is a respite (a second blow after the first). This respite – even if long – is not felt by people because they are in a state of unconsciousness (fainting).

The stage of wakefulness (the second blow): Allah sends consciousness and perception into the forms, and they stand and look. This stage parallels "then I blow" in the story of Jesus, and parallels "Fayakun" in the creative command.

And the miracle is that Jesus gathered the two stages in a single moment (using the Fa for immediate sequence) as a sign of Allah's power. But on the Day of Resurrection, there is a respite between the two stages – even if not felt by people – to allow the scenes of resurrection, the Sirat (bridge), and the reckoning to be manifested.

Conclusion of the Research

After applying the linguistic equation and the parallel with the Quranic models, inductively studying the meaning of "Qarn" in the Quran, using evidence from the verses of Al-Waqi'ah that resurrection is a new genesis, the context of Surat Az-Zumar which proves that fainting is a physiological revival, the verses of "Labithna" which prove that the duration between the two blows was a short, felt period, reading the prophetic hadith in light of the Quranic usage of the word "Qarn", the foundational study of the word "buq" which proves it is a foreign loanword not present at the time of Prophethood, and adding the study of the verse "Everyone upon it will perish" and the verse "From it We created you" which confirm that death is a perishing and resurrection is a new genesis from the earth, and what was narrated from Imam Al-Hasan bin Ali, the grandson of the Messenger of Allah, that he interpreted Al-Sur as the plural of "Surah" – a statement from the first century AH – and the addition of the study of the formula "Kun Fayakun" which proves that revival does not require intermediaries and that blowing into Al-Sur is the practical application of this formula, the research favors that interpreting "Al-Sur" as forms and bodies is the strongest view, because:

It is consistent with the linguistic equation: Inclination → Form → Sartahu.

It matches the Quranic models of revival in the stories of Adam, Abraham, Jesus, and Mary.

It explains the fainting in the verse of Az-Zumar as physiological revival (unconsciousness).

It directs the pronoun in "Then it is blown again (Thumma nufikha fihi ukhra)" to the forms, with a morphological study proving the permissibility of the masculine pronoun referring to a feminine plural.

It explains the exception in the two verses of An-Naml and Az-Zumar as including martyrs and the close angels.

It connects the second blow to the divine call in the verse of Al-Isra.

It reconciles the verse of Az-Zumar which mentions two blows with the rest of the verses of Al-Sur which mention one blow.

It makes the authentic hadith ("Al-Sur is a horn that is blown into") not contradictory to the hypothesis, by interpreting "Qarn" in its established Quranic meaning (the nation) while retaining the apparent meaning of the instrument within a reconciliatory framework.

The foundational study of the word "buq" proves it is a foreign loanword, confirming that interpreting the hadith's "Qarn" as a "trumpet" is a later scholarly ijihad.

The verse "Everyone upon it will perish" confirms that death is a cessation with no sensation.

The verse "From it We created you..." confirms that resurrection is a re-creation from the earth.

The statement of Imam Al-Hasan bin Ali bin Abi Talib, the grandson of the Messenger of Allah, that Al-Sur is the plural of Surah was known in early exegesis from the first century AH, giving the hypothesis significant historical weight.

The study of the formula "Kun Fayakun" proves that revival does not require intermediaries, and that blowing into Al-Sur is the practical application of this formula, strengthening the interpretation of "Al-Sur" as the forms into which the spirit is blown directly.

After this inductive study and analysis, the research reaches two main conclusions:

First: That the word "Al-Sur" in the Holy Quran is – in the stronger view – the plural of "Surah" meaning the forms and bodies into which the resurrection blow is blown, as narrated from Imam Al-Hasan bin Ali, the grandson of the Prophet, and indicated by Az-Zajjaj, At-Tabarsi, Qatadah, and Abu Ubaidah.

Second: That the word "buq" (trumpet) is a foreign, loanword in Arabic, not present at the time of Prophethood nor in the Holy Quran, and interpreting the hadith "Al-Sur is a horn that is blown into" as meaning "buq" is a later exegetical ijtiḥad.

And Allah knows best.

Completed with the help of Allah.

List of Sources and References

The Holy Quran.

Al-Azhari, Muhammad bin Ahmad. Tahdhib Al-Lughah. Edited by Muhammad Awad Mur'ib. Beirut: Dar Ihya' Al-Turath Al-Arabi, 2001.

Al-Alusi, Shihab Al-Din Mahmoud. Ruh Al-Ma'ani fi Tafsir Al-Quran Al-Azim wa Al-Sab' Al-Mathani. Beirut: Dar Ihya' Al-Turath Al-Arabi, 1415 AH.

Ibn Al-Jawzi, Abd Al-Rahman bin Ali. Zad Al-Masir fi Ilm Al-Tafsir. Edited by Abd Al-Razzaq Al-Mahdi. Beirut: Dar Al-Kitab Al-Arabi, 1422 AH.

Ibn Jinni, Uthman. Al-Khasa'is. Edited by Muhammad Ali Al-Najjar. Cairo: Egyptian General Book Authority, n.d.

Ibn Hajar Al-Asqalani, Ahmad bin Ali. Al-Isabah fi Tamyiz Al-Sahabah. Edited by Adel Ahmad Abd Al-Mawjud and Ali Muhammad Mu'awwad. Beirut: Dar Al-Kutub Al-Ilmiyyah, 1415 AH.

Ibn Duraid, Muhammad bin Al-Hasan. Jamharat Al-Lughah. Edited by Ramzi Muneer Ba'albaki. Beirut: Dar Al-Ilm Lil Malayin, 1987.

Ibn Faris, Ahmad. Maqayis Al-Lughah. Edited by Abd Al-Salam Harun. Beirut: Dar Al-Jeel, 1411 AH.

Ibn Kathir, Isma'il. Tafsir Al-Quran Al-Azim. Edited by Sami bin Muhammad Al-Salamah. Riyadh: Dar Tayyibah, 1420 AH.

Ibn Manzur, Muhammad bin Makram. Lisan Al-Arab. Beirut: Dar Sadir, n.d.

Ibn Hisham, Abd Allah bin Yusuf. Mughni Al-Labib an Kutub Al-A'arib. Edited by Mazin Al-Mubarak. Beirut: Dar Al-Fikr, 1405 AH.

Ibn Al-Qayyim, Muhammad bin Abi Bakr. Madarij Al-Salikin bayna Manazil Iyyaka Na'budu wa Iyyaka Nasta'in. Edited by Muhammad Al-Mu'tasim Billah Al-Baghdadi. Beirut: Dar Al-Kitab Al-Arabi, 1416 AH.

Ibn Al-Qayyim, Muhammad bin Abi Bakr. Al-Sawa'iq Al-Mursala ala Al-Jahmiyyah wa Al-Mu'attilah. Edited by Abd Al-Rahman bin Hasan Qa'id. Riyadh: Dar Al-Asimah, 1418 AH.

Ibn Malik, Muhammad bin Abd Allah. Sharh Al-Kafiyah Al-Shafiyah. Edited by Abd Al-Mun'im Haridi. Mecca: Umm Al-Qura University, 1402 AH.

Ibn Ashur, Muhammad Al-Tahir. Al-Tahrir wa Al-Tanwir. Tunis: Al-Dar Al-Tunisiyyah Lil Nashr, 1984.

Abu Dawud, Sulayman bin Al-Ash'ath. Sunan Abi Dawud. Edited by Muhammad Muhyi Al-Din Abd Al-Hamid. Beirut: Al-Maktabah Al-Asriyyah, n.d.

Ahmad bin Hanbal. Al-Musnad. Edited by Shu'ayb Al-Arna'ut and others. Beirut: Mu'assasat Al-Risalah, 1421 AH.

Al-Khalil bin Ahmad Al-Farahidi. Kitab Al-Ain. Edited by Mahdi Al-Makhzumi and Ibrahim Al-Samarra'i. Beirut: Dar wa Maktabat Al-Hilal, n.d.

Al-Razi, Fakhr Al-Din. Mafatih Al-Ghayb (Al-Tafsir Al-Kabir). Beirut: Dar Ihya' Al-Turath Al-Arabi, 1420 AH.

Al-Raghib Al-Isfahani, Al-Husayn bin Muhammad. Al-Mufradat fi Gharib Al-Quran. Edited by Safwan Adnan Al-Dawoodi. Damascus: Dar Al-Qalam, 1412 AH.

Al-Zubaidi, Muhammad Murtada. Taj Al-Arus min Jawahir Al-Qamus. Edited by a group of investigators. Kuwait: Dar Al-Hidayah, n.d.

Al-Zajjaj, Ibrahim bin Al-Sari. Ma'ani Al-Quran wa l'rabuhu. Edited by Abd Al-Jalil Abduh Shalabi. Beirut: Alam Al-Kutub, 1408 AH.

Al-Zamakhshari, Mahmoud bin Umar. Al-Kashshaf an Haqa'iq Ghawamid Al-Tanzil. Edited by Muhammad Husayn Ahmad. Beirut: Dar Al-Ma'rifah, 1407 AH.

Sibawayh, Amr bin Uthman. Al-Kitab. Edited by Abd Al-Salam Harun. Cairo: Egyptian General Book Authority, 1408 AH.

Al-Tabari, Muhammad bin Jarir. Jami' Al-Bayan an Ta'wil Ay Al-Quran. Edited by Ahmad Muhammad Shakir. Cairo: Mu'assasat Al-Risalah, 1420 AH.

Al-Tabarsi, Al-Fadl bin Al-Hasan. Majma' Al-Bayan fi Tafsir Al-Quran. Edited by Muhammad Jawad Shari'atmadari. Beirut: Dar Al-Ma'rifah, 1408 AH.

Al-Tusi, Muhammad bin Al-Hasan. Al-Tibyan Al-Jami' li Ulum Al-Quran. Edited by Ahmad Habib Qasir Al-Amili. Beirut: Dar Ihya' Al-Turath Al-Arabi, n.d.

Al-Tirmidhi, Muhammad bin Isa. Sunan Al-Tirmidhi. Edited by Ahmad Muhammad Shakir. Beirut: Dar Ihya' Al-Turath Al-Arabi, n.d.

Al-Qurtubi, Muhammad bin Ahmad. Al-Jami' li Ahkam Al-Quran. Edited by Ahmad Al-Barduni and Ibrahim Atfish. Cairo: Dar Al-Kutub Al-Misriyyah, 1384 AH.

Al-Farra', Yahya bin Ziyad. Ma'ani Al-Quran. Edited by Ahmad Yusuf Najati. Cairo: Dar Al-Kutub Al-Misriyyah, n.d.

Dozy, Reinhart. Takmilat Al-Ma'ajim Al-Arabiyyah (Supplement to Arabic Dictionaries).
Translated by Muhammad Salim Al-Nu'aimi. Baghdad: Ministry of Culture and Information, 1980.